

ANALYSIS OF OUTLIER INFLUENCE ON NONLINEAR FILTER OUTPUT FOR LINEARLY INCREASING/DECREASING SIGNALS WITH NOISE

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ABSTRACT

The influence of an outlier present in a scanning window on nonlinear filter output characteristics like bias and variance is analyzed using output distributional influence functions and estimates of statistical parameters by computer simulation. The standard median, Wilcoxon and α -trimmed filters with different scanning window sizes are considered. The peculiarity of signal model is that besides constant signals we exploit the linearly increasing/decreasing ones. It is shown that there exist specific peculiarities of filter output behavior depending upon noise variance, outlier and signal derivative signs and values. Filter output bias and variance also depend on filter type and scanning window size. All these effects should be taken into account in many practical applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

In many real world situations the noise corrupting the signal is not Gaussian. For example it can be the superposition of additive zero-mean Gaussian and impulsive noise components. Linear filters do not perform well in case of impulse (outlier) presence. On the contrary, nonlinear filters are known to be able to remove outliers from a data sequence to be processed [1], [2]. However, even for nonlinear filters the presence of an outlier in a scanning window can cause specific errors like jitter effect in the neighborhood of a step edge [1].

Moreover, even for constant signals the impulsive noise presence results in changing the statistical characteristics of the nonlinear filter output. An efficient tool called output distributional influence function (ODIF) just suited for analyzing such effects has been designed recently [3]. It shows the robustness of finite sample estimators. As many nonlinear filters are based on such estimators and they perform data processing in scanning windows of finite size,

an approach of filter output analysis using ODIF occurs to be very effective.

Even in the case of outlier absence the nonlinear filters have efficiency of Gaussian noise suppression dependent on signal properties. In [4] it is shown that for linearly increasing/decreasing signal (LIDS) the efficiency of noise suppression for standard median and some other nonlinear filters can be considerably worse than for constant signals. A particular example given in [4] also demonstrates that for LIDS the outlier present in the scanning window results in a specific effect in filter output in the neighborhood of data sample corrupted by the spike. This effect is very similar to jitter but it appears in several samples.

In general, this happens not only for standard median filter but for many other nonlinear filters as well. For locally adaptive filters based on nonlinear filter bank [5] this question is also important since it is not clear yet what filter is it reasonable to apply in case of spike presence for LIDS fragments of the signal. So our main goal is to study such situations and to quantitatively evaluate the observed effects.

2. SIGNAL/NOISE MODEL AND THE PROBLEM STATEMENT

Let us consider the following signal/noise model of the sampled data $\{U(t_i)\}, i = 1, \dots, I$

$$U(t_i) = \begin{cases} S(t_i) + n_a(t_i), & \text{with probability } 1 - P_{imp} \\ S(t_i) + A_i(t_i), & \text{with probability } P_{imp} \end{cases}, \quad (1)$$

where $S(t_i)$ is the true signal value of the i -th sample; n_a is the zero mean additive Gaussian noise with the variance σ^2 ; A_i defines the amplitude of the impulsive noise occur-

ring with the probability $P_{imp}(|A_i| >> 3\sigma)$. As we consider the LIDS, then $S(t_i) = k_0(t_i - t_0)$ where k_0 and t_0 are constants, and $\Delta t = t_i - t_{i-1}$ is the sampling rate. We also assumed in simulations that the amplitude of the spike is rather large ($|A_i| > 3\sigma + k_0\Delta t(N-1)/2$), i.e. if the outlier is present in the scanning window of size N then the value of the sample corrupted by the outlier is either the largest or the smallest among all the values in the scanning window.

The considered fragmentary model of signal and noise corresponds to many practical situations. The linearly increasing/decreasing signals are observed in ECG-signals (their QRS complex fragment). Another example is a sequence of angle coordinate estimates of some object that moves with constant velocity. In this case the signal component $S(t_i)$ is the sequence of true values of coordinates and n_a or A_i can be referred to normal and abnormal errors of coordinate estimates, respectively.

In computer simulations it was supposed that there is only one data sample corrupted by impulse and its index i_0 was always equal to 17. Due to this it was possible to consider the filter output characteristics mainly in the neighborhood of this sample. In our simulations the additive noise variance σ^2 was constant and equal to 0.003 ($\sigma=0.055$) and the slope k_0 was varied to provide different ratios $\Delta S/\sigma$ (from 0 to 5) where $\Delta S = k_0\Delta t$.

3. ODIF ANALYSIS

Several nonlinear filters have been considered. They are the standard median filter, the Wilcoxon filter known to be an effective smoother and quite robust estimator, and the α -trimmed filter (with $\alpha \approx 0.2$ to provide correctness of results in comparison with Wilcoxon filter) [2]. The studied values of N varied from 5 to 11.

The ODIF for the expectation is similar to the influence function but it is defined for the finite length filters and the distribution function of the contamination is not limited to be Δ_y but can be any distribution function G_y (See [3] and references therein). In Fig.1 we display the ODIFs for the expectation of the median filter ($N=5$) of an increasing signal ($\Delta S/\sigma = 1.0$) with Gaussian noise $\sigma^2 = 0.03$ where different graphs are obtained by adding the infinitesimal contamination with distribution Δ_y to one sample at a time. From these graphs we can see how different the influence of the infinitesimal contamination is on filter robustness (characterized by ODIF) depending on which sample of the increasing signal we add it to. As seen when A_i becomes large enough the filter output bias remains the same

irrespective of the spike amplitude. Moreover, ODIF analysis permits to predict that for LIDS the biased area can be shifted in respect to the true position of the spike (see next Section and Fig.4).

Fig.1. The ODIFs for the expectation of median filter ($N=5$) for linearly increasing signal ($\Delta S/\sigma = 1.0$) with Gaussian noise $\sigma^2 = 0.03$. The highest graph (solid line) is the one where the leftmost sample in the window is contaminated by infinitesimal contamination with distribution Δ_y .

Due to lack of space we present in this paper mainly the simulation results. However, for the median and the α -trimmed filter it is possible to derive the distribution function of the output and the computer simulation results (See next Section) are in good agreement with the theoretical ones for small filter lengths. The theoretical data calculations become very complicated and time consuming when the filter length increases. Because of this numerical analysis is better in such situations. For Wilcoxon filter even the derivation of the output distribution function is too laborious.

4. NUMERICAL SIMULATION RESULTS

Let us analyze some computer simulation results. First of all, it is worth saying that by averaging the outputs of every considered filter it is possible to estimate the output bias as a function of index i in the following way: $\Delta D = E\{U^f(t_i) - S(t_i)\}$ where E denotes expectation calculation and $U^f(t_i)$ is the filter output. As is seen from Fig. 2,a, even for constant signal the presence of outlier in the scanning window results in filter output bias approximately equal to 0.3σ for standard median filter and increasing up to approximately 0.5σ for Wilcoxon filter. The size of the area with bias is determined by the scanning window size.

Fig. 2,a. Filter output bias for different types of filters for $\Delta S/\sigma=0; N=5$.

As it can be seen in Fig.2,b, for larger N the bias area width becomes larger but the output bias reduces for all the considered filters. In both cases the α -trimmed filters take the intermediate places between the Wilcoxon and standard median filters.

Fig. 2,b. Filter output bias for different types of filters for $\Delta S/\sigma=0; N=9$.

For LIDS (see Fig.3,a and 3,b) the bias also takes place. Moreover, despite the noise variance is the same the bias is essentially larger than in the case of constant signal. An interesting aspect is that the bias is not equal for all samples in the neighborhood of the spiky sample. The maximal bias approximately equals to ΔS and this is valid for different ratios of $\Delta S/\sigma$. This means that the filter output signal shifts to the next or previous value of true signal like in edge jittering. The width of biased area for given N depends upon filter type and it is more narrow for standard median filter than for the other two considered filter types. With increasing N the width of output bias area also becomes larger (compare results in Fig. 3,a and 3,b).

Finally, the bias sign and the biased area location depend upon the signs of k_0 and A_i . It is clearly seen in Fig.4 where different possible situations are analyzed. When the sign of k_0 is the same but the sign of A_i is different the areas of the output biased values are shifted with respect to each other. The output signal bias can be considered as a specific type of dynamic errors in nonlinear filters.

a)

b)

Fig. 3. Filter output bias for different types of filters: a) $\Delta S/\sigma=1; N=5$; b) $\Delta S/\sigma=1; N=9$.

Fig.4. Dependence of median filter output bias upon signal and noise parameters ($N=5; \Delta S/\sigma=1$).

However, the presence of a spike in the scanning window results not only in output bias but in increase in the output variance in the spike neighborhood as well. This is explained by the fact that in the case of spike presence less sample values "take part in averaging process".

First, consider a constant valued signal. The variance of its output calculated with respect to the output mean (i.e. without taking bias into account) is presented in Fig.5 for $N=5$. It is well seen that for the standard median filter, in general, the value is considerably larger than for Wilcoxon and α -trimmed filters. This is in agreement with the theory [2]. But in the neighborhood of the impulse the variance increases and the size of this area is equal to the scanning window size N .

Fig.5. Output variance for different types of filters for $\Delta S/\sigma=0; N=5$.

The case of larger N is similar and the corresponding plots are shown in Fig.6. However, the relative increase of variance values in the neighborhood of the spiky sample is smaller than for $N=5$.

Fig.6. Output variance for different types of filters for $\Delta S/\sigma=0; N=9$.

Let us now consider the LIDS. The output variance for small scanning window size is given in Fig.7. The maxima of the output variance are a little bit shifted with respect to $i_0=17$. An interesting fact is that the variance for the standard median filter becomes considerably larger than for the other two filters as shown in [4].

For larger N the increase of output variance in the spike neighborhood is less noticeable for median filter and almost not observed for the other considered nonlinear filters (See Fig.8).

CONCLUSIONS

The investigation carried out demonstrates that the outlier presence in data sequence can lead to peculiar effects in the output signals even if one applies nonlinear filters for the outlier removal. The influence of the outliers occurs to be especially considerable for linearly increasing/decreasing signals. The effects discussed in this paper can lead to errors in signal parameter estimation and they should be taken into account while selecting a proper filter for signal processing application at hand.

Fig.7. Output variance for different types of filters for $\Delta S/\sigma=1; N=5$.

Fig.8. Output variance for different types of filters for $\Delta S/\sigma=1; N=9$.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. T. Astola, P. Kuosmanen, Fundamentals of Nonlinear Digital Filtering, New York, NY: CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1997.
- [2] I. Pitas, A. N. Venetsanopoulos, Nonlinear Digital Filters: Principles and Applications, New York: Kluwer Academic Publishers, 1990.
- [3] S. Peltonen, P. Kuosmanen, J. Astola, "Output distributional influence functions", Proceedings of the IEEE-EURASIP Workshop on Nonlinear Signal and Image Processing, Antalya, Turkey, June 1999, V.1, pp. 33-37.
- [4] K. Willner, P. Kuosmanen, V. Lukin, A. Pogrebniak, "Nonlinear filters and rapidly increasing/decreasing signals corrupted with noise", CD-ROM Proceedings of Nonlinear Signal/Image Processing (NSIP) Conference, Michigan, USA, Sept. 1997, 5 pages.
- [5] V. V. Lukin, N. O. Tuliakova, V. P. Melnik, A. A. Zelensky, "Adaptive method for 1-D signal processing based on nonlinear filter bank and Z-parameter", Proceedings of the IEEE-EURASIP Workshop on Nonlinear Signal and Image Processing, Antalya, Turkey, June 1999, V.1, pp. 287-291.